

Paste your Photograph Here

Paste your Logo here

Title: Transfer Learning and One-Shot Learning: Commercial Success Key

Name: Amita Kapoor¹ and Narotam Singh²

Affiliation: ¹Shaheed Rajguru College of Applied Sciences for Women, University of Delhi, Delhi, India.

²Information Communication and Instrumentation Training Center, India Meteorological Department, Ministry of Earth Sciences, Delhi, India.

INTRODUCTION:

In the last one-decade, deep neural architectures, guided by supervised learning have been the major source of the success of machine learning. These deep neural networks have two key requirements immensely huge labelled data and computationally efficient hardware (GPUs). While such immensely large data exists for some tasks and domains, in most cases the data are usually proprietary or expensive. This is a hindrance for rapid deployment of AI based applications by both companies and small entrepreneurs. To deal with these issues researcher developed techniques of Transfer Learning and one-shot learning for using pre-trained deep neural networks on different domains and label space. Transfer Learning is the technique to use models pre-trained on one domain for another problem domain, they provide us the ability to use DNNs even when the dataset is small. One shot learning aims to learn the label space from one or only a few training samples. In this paper we will present some successful case-studies of the application of transfer learning and one-shot learning.

AIM:

To present some successful case-studies for the application of transfer learning and one-shot learning

DATASET AND METHODS:

- 1. Dog Breed Identification:** We used pretrained Resnet, Inception, Xception and VGG networks to identify the breed of a given dog. We removed the fully connected layers of these models and used instead our own fully connected layers, which were fine tuned to categorize a given dog image to its right breed.

- 2. Emotion Detection:** Here again we used the pretrained Resnet, Inception, Xception and VGG networks to detect emotion from facial images. But instead of just fine tuning the top layers, we freeze the lower CNN layers, and train the upper layers.

RESULTS: For the dog breed identification, the results of transfer learning were compared by the results obtained from CNNs train from scratched. The CNN network with 91,829 training parameters was able to give only 18.2% accuracy. On the hand with only 436, 933 training parameters, we could increase efficiency upto 85%. Similar results were obtained for Emotion Detection on FER2013 dataset.

CONCLUSIONS:

Transfer Learning and one shot learning significantly reduce the training time, without sacrificing the accuracy. Thus, they can help in reducing the production time for AI/ML applications.

KEYWORDS:

Transfer Learning, One Shot Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks, Artificial Intelligence, Deep Learning

BIOGRAPHY:

Amita Kapoor is Associate Professor in the Department of Electronics, SRCASW, University of Delhi. She has been actively teaching neural networks for last twenty years. She did her Masters in Electronics in the year 1996, and her Ph.D. in the year 2011. During her Ph.D., she was awarded prestigious DAAD fellowship to pursue a part of her research work in Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Karlsruhe, Germany. She has more than 40 publications in the international journals and conferences. She is also author of the book Tensorflow 1.x Deep Learning Cookbook by Packt Publishers

Narotam Singh is Assistant Meteorologist-II at India Metrological Department, Ministry of Earth Sciences. His job profile involves teaching and research at Information Communication and Instrumentation Training Center. He did his Masters in the field of Electronics from Jamia Milia Islamia in the year 1996, and graduation in Physics (Hons.) from University of Delhi in the year 1993. He also holds diploma and postgraduate diploma in the field Computer Applications. His present research interests involve neural networks, Internet of things, Robotics and Buddhism.